

Impact Study Improving Scientific Practices

Improving Scientific Practices

Context

Biodata resources provide standardised, high-quality data and enforce rigorous quality control measures that directly affect the applicability and reliability of follow-on work. They contribute to creating practices that multidisciplinary communities – within and beyond academia – can adopt when sharing and reusing information generated by others across different regions of the world. A shared language, which can be embodied by agreed-upon metadata fields, definitions and taxonomies, is essential to collaborate on the global stage.

The role of biodata resources in shaping and improving scientific practices is significant as we shift towards increased use of computer-based analytics and drug discovery, which require standardisation and machine readability to be effectively applied. These case studies explore some of the ways in which biodata resources have been influencing the ways in which scientists work.

Enabling traceable and reproducible research

[Cellosaurus](#) is a biodata resource providing information on over 150,000 cell lines, including human, mouse and rat, for use in biomedical research. Cell lines are derived from primary cells isolated from living tissue, but have been genetically modified to allow them to proliferate indefinitely under appropriate culture conditions. They are widely used for cancer research, drug discovery, vaccine development and genetic studies.

Cellosaurus provides each cell line with a persistent and unique identifier called a [Research Resource Identifier \(RRID\)](#). Persistent identifiers are especially important in the context of the so-called ‘reproducibility crisis’ that continues to fill headlines in science reporting alongside high-profile retractions. In essence, growing numbers of published works are being questioned on the grounds that the claims they make cannot be verified by third parties by applying the stated methodology to samples or data originally used by the authors. By providing standardised, persistent identifiers for cell lines, Cellosaurus ensures that researchers can accurately reference and verify the exact biological materials used in experiments, ultimately improving traceability and reproducibility in biomedical research.

Data from Cellosaurus also informs the [Register of Misidentified Cell Lines](#), which is curated by the International Cell Line Authentication Committee (ICLAC) and covers cell lines that are known to be misidentified through cross-contamination or other mechanisms (e.g., mislabelling). This issue has important repercussions: for example, research has [identified](#) a total of 21 cell lines still used in hepatology that have been misidentified as being of hepatic origin.

One example is cell line H-7721, which was identified as contaminated almost 20 years ago but is still used frequently in hepatology research. By using data from Cellosaurus and the Register of Misidentified Cell Lines, alongside improved reporting guidelines in authentication and training on good cell culture practice, researchers can reduce the number of papers reporting results with misidentified or cross-contaminated cell lines.

Additionally, a 2019 [study](#) identifying 305,161 unique cell-line names in 150,459 articles estimated that 8.6% of these cell lines were on the list of problematic cell lines. While using [problematic cell lines](#) does not automatically mean that a line is being used improperly, researchers should aim to use appropriate identifiers to enable the accurate interpretation of their research findings.

Upholding high quality standards

The [ENCODE \(Encyclopedia of DNA Elements\)](#) project is a comprehensive effort to identify and catalogue all functional elements in the human genome. It provides a parts list of functional elements in the human genome, including elements that act at the protein and RNA levels, and regulatory elements that control cells and circumstances in which a gene is active.

This initiative is actively involved in developing and enforcing quality standards. The ENCODE Consortium uses various metrics to evaluate the quality of data produced and categorise it as excellent, passable, or poor, based on a suite of purpose-developed [software tools](#) and [metrics](#). They employ standard formats for data submission that capture all relevant parameters and experimental conditions, with a dedicated quality assurance team reviewing all data before public release. Furthermore, the ENCODE portal offers extensive documentation, tutorials and interactive guides to assist researchers in understanding and using ENCODE metadata and data effectively.

ENCODE is broadly recognised as a major contributor to our understanding of the regulation of the genome from many perspectives. These include transcriptomes and gene regulation, the 3D organisation of the genome, RNA bindings, regulation, and more. Additionally, data from ENCODE has also been used to predict new candidate drugs, that, for example, alter transcription factor activity in specific diseases and to identify molecules that can indirectly modulate transcription factors of interest.

Conclusions

The impact of biodata resources on standards and good practice is significant: increasing the traceability and quality standards of research data contributes to the reduction of wasted efforts, with positive repercussions on public sector spend (e.g. in the case of publicly funded research) and on the establishment of industry priorities (e.g. in the case of a company deciding what R&D areas to prioritise).

By providing a standardised source of information, biodata resources can enable researchers and companies alike to create cutting-edge solutions that have the potential to transform healthcare and improve patient outcomes. As the biomedical research community continues to evolve towards computationally intensive approaches, challenges around reproducibility and data quality will grow in magnitude, underscoring the role of these resources in enhancing the integrity and reliability of findings.

References

- Cellosaurus - Cell line encyclopedia (n.d.) Cellosaurus. Available at: <https://www.cellosaurus.org/> (Accessed: 16 September 2024).
- ENCODE 3 (2020) Nature. Available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/d42859-020-00027-2> (Accessed: 16 September 2024).
- Getting Started – ENCODE (n.d.) ENCODE. Available at: <https://www.encodeproject.org/help/getting-started/> (Accessed: 16 September 2024).
- Overview of the Research Identification Initiative (no date) Cellosaurus. Available at: <https://www.cellosaurus.org/> (Accessed: 16 September 2024).
- Reducing the Improper Use of Cell Lines (2019) GEN - Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology News. Available at: <https://www.genengnews.com/news/reducing-the-improper-use-of-cell-lines/> (Accessed: 16 September 2024).
- Register of Misidentified Cell Lines (n.d.) ICLAC. Available at: <https://iclac.org/databases/cross-contaminations/> (Accessed: 16 September 2024).
- Software Tools – ENCODE (n.d.). Available at: <https://www.encodeproject.org/software/> (Accessed: 16 September 2024).
- Terms and Definitions – ENCODE (n.d.). Available at: <https://www.encodeproject.org/data-standards/terms/> (Accessed: 16 September 2024).
- Zhao, Y., Schaafsma, E. and Cheng, C. (2018) 'Applications of ENCODE data to systematic analyses via data integration', Current Opinion in Systems Biology, 11, pp. 57–64. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coisb.2018.08.010>.

Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
Cellosaurus	Cellosaurus is a resource for cell lines used in biomedical research (with the exception of primary cell lines). As of 2022, it hosts more than 144,000 cell lines and their related information. Cellosaurus is a participant of the Resource Identification Initiative and a contributor to the International Cell Line Authentication Committee.

[Encyclopedia of DNA Elements Consortium \(ENCODE\)](#)

The ENCODE consortium is an international collaboration funded by the National Human Genome Research Institute. It aims to build a parts list of functional elements in the human genome, including those at the protein and RNA level and those that control the cell.

ENCODE began in 2003 and has gone through several production scale-effort phases, known as ENCODE 2 and ENCODE 3

Global Biodata Coalition

- 🌐 www.globalbiodata.org
- ✉ info@globalbiodata.org
- x [@globalbiodata](https://twitter.com/globalbiodata)
- in [@globalbiodatacoalition](https://www.linkedin.com/company/globalbiodatacoalition)

A digital version of this publication is available at :

www.globalbiodata.org/news-and-resources/

The GBC acknowledges the work of [Research Consulting](#) in the preparation of these impact studies.

